

ISic2919

I.Sicily inscription 2919

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.09.09

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni (entrance)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 29652

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Iulia]nus gub[ernator]
2. [prosu]miarum [hiciacet]
3. [pater] contra b[otumfecit]
4. [toties] p(ost) c(onsuli) Basili v(iri) c(larissimi) ind(ictione) tali

Apparatus

Text after Ferrua 1989

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645308

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 354B(1)

Diehl, Ernst Johann L. 1925. *Inscriptiones Latinae Christianae Veteres*. Berlin. At 568A

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*.

Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 581

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.

Vatican. At no.97a

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